

Path Representation in Circuit Netlists Using Linear-Sized ZDDs with Optimal Variable Ordering

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Abstract The efficient representation and manipulation of a large number of paths in a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) requires the usage of special data structures that may become of exponential size with respect to the size of the graph. Several methodologies targeting Electronic Design Automation problems such as timing analysis, physical design, verification and testing involve path representation and necessary manipulation. Previous works proposed an encoding using Zero-suppressed Binary Decision Diagrams (ZDDs), which has been shown experimentally to cope well when representing structural or logical paths in VLSI circuits. However, it is well known that the ordering of the variables in a ZDD highly affects its size and, therefore, the efficiency of the methodologies utilizing these data structures. In this work, we show that using a reverse topological order for the ZDD variables bounds the number of nodes in the ZDD representing structural paths to the number of edges in the DAG considered, hence, making the ZDD size linear to the DAG's size. This result, supported here both theoretically and experimentally, is very important as it can render methodologies with questionable scalability applicable to larger industrial designs. We demonstrate the applicability of

the proposed variable ordering in one such methodology which utilizes ZDDs to grade the Path Delay Fault coverage of a given test set.

Keywords Paths Representation · Binary Decision Diagrams · Path Delay Fault Simulation and Test · Timing Analysis · Timing Verification.

1 Introduction

Theoretic approaches that use graphs, mathematical structures representing relationships using vertices and edges [18], have been used to solve problems in a plethora of scientific disciplines. From linguistics to biology and from sociology to software development all kind of problems have been mapped into graphs and solved using graph theoretic algorithms. Problems such as pattern matching for DNA sequences [47], speech recognition [27], data mining [21], identifying dependencies in programming language compilers [45], finding the optimal route in a communication [9] or transportation [19] network, logic synthesis of electronic circuits [12], among others, require path representation and manipulation.

A special case of such graphs, with important significance, is the Directed Acyclic Graph (DAGs) whose edges are unidirectional and no loops are allowed within the structure. While DAGs are restricted graphs, many algorithms have been developed based on them, (or on some variation), finding many applications in science and engineering. A number of problems using DAGs deal with the identification, representation, traversal and/or enumeration of the graph paths. In the general case, the number of paths in a DAG can be exponential to the number of vertices in the graph. As a result, both the data structure used and the algorithms developed should be chosen carefully in order to keep

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the computational effort manageable (i.e., not requiring prohibitively large memory space). In essence, the potentially large number of paths in, even medium sized DAGs, does not permit the usage of any kind of path-enumerative steps in these algorithms.

In traditional VLSI design, DAGs have been extensively used for representing circuit netlists and physical design layouts. In the area of Electronic Design Automation (EDA) the usage of DAGs has been extended to include logic synthesis, module dependencies identification, timing analysis, design verification, post-manufacturing testing, among others [46]. Many of the proposed methodologies targeting these problems involve the graph's paths and corresponding operations on them such as path matching [1, 29], identifying paths with specific size [3, 38], identifying path overlap [33], union and intersection on path sets [7], etc.

A number of previous works considering applications in EDA [8, 25, 30, 32, 36, 40, 44] have shown that paths can be represented compactly using Zero-Suppressed Ordered Binary Decision Diagrams (ZDDs) [31], a variant of Binary Decision Diagrams [6]. This representation is very important since the performance of the basic operations on a ZDD is linear to its size. Hence, the majority of the problems mentioned here can be efficiently solved, considering the ZDD-based representation of the paths rather than the traditional DAG representing the circuit's netlist. However, these works do not address explicitly, nor adequately, the issue of the ZDD size which depends on the order of its variables. The importance of using ZDDs for efficient representation of paths in a graph is discussed in [23] where the author proposed a solution where the ZDD representing the paths in a DAG has the same "shape" as the DAG itself. In the same work, an algorithm for efficient path representation for *general graphs* is proposed (as the solution to exercise 225, later named SIMPATH) but with no theoretical result bounding the ZDD size. The work in [22] implements SIMPATH and provides experimental data which demonstrate non-linear size for the obtained ZDD. More importantly, the algorithm cannot be trivially extended to directed graphs, which is what it is considered in this work.

In this work we prove that the space requirement (i.e., number of ZDD nodes) of a ZDD representing all paths in a DAG is linear to the number of DAG vertices, when a reverse topological order on the ZDD's variables is considered. In this context, the netlist of a fully-scanned or combinational circuit is used as the input corresponding to the DAG. For the path representation the non-enumerative mapping proposed in [36] is employed. A theoretical analysis examines the effect of the topological variable ordering on the ZDD size. Our

analysis concludes that the reverse topological order produces ZDDs with size equal to the number of the circuit's lines, for the mapping considered. The theoretical findings are also experimentally validated by building all paths for benchmark circuits (including several path-intensive ones) under four different orderings in order to demonstrate the impact of the proposed variable ordering. [Preliminary evidence of the proposed variable order as well as preliminary experimental results have been presented in \[34\].](#) In this work we provide a complete theoretical analysis of the problem examined. Moreover, we present new experimental results that demonstrate that the proposed static ordering method is superior to a dynamic approach. Finally, one of the numerous possible applications of the presented theoretical result, that of Path Delay Fault (PDF) test grading, is used to demonstrate the impact of the proposed variable ordering on the method of [36] and its later extension in [25].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes previous work for path and PDF representation as well as the path mapping considered in this work. Section 3 gives the path construction algorithm and shows that the representation requires linear, to the input DAG size, space when considering reverse topological variable order. Section 4 presents and discusses the obtained experimental results and corresponding findings. Section 5 demonstrates how PDF grading benefits from using the proposed ordering while Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 Preliminaries and Related Work

2.1 ZDD-based Path Representation

Zero-Suppressed Ordered Binary Decision Diagrams (ZDDs) are graphical representations of Boolean functions where a node corresponds to a boolean variable and an outgoing node edge corresponds to a 0 or 1 decision for the variable. They are ordered/levelized diagrams, and their shape and size depends on the ordering of the variables which dictates which variable corresponds to each level in the diagram. They obey specific decomposition and reduction rules which make them compact and unique, given a specific variable order. ZDDs in particular are ideal for representing sparse binary combinational sets, since they are based on the underlying decomposition rule that 0 values in a combination can be often suppressed which means that no corresponding node is necessary. For an in-depth discussion on these well known diagrams, the reader is referred to [6, 31].

Fig. 1 Circuit C17 from ISCAS’85 benchmark suite: (a) netlist representation and (b) the corresponding DAG (where a vertex v_i corresponds to netlist line i).

In [36] a circuit structural path is encoded in a ZDD as a binary combination. A structural path is a complete I/O path, comprised of consecutive circuit interconnection lines. The encoding considers one ZDD variable per circuit line. For each variable, one or more nodes may exist at the same level in the ZDD. Each node has two children (corresponding to the two possible decisions) reached by a 0-edge or a 1-edge. Following a path in the ZDD an outgoing 1-edge from a node means that the variable corresponding to the node exists (=1) in the combination. A 0-edge means that the corresponding variable does not exist (=0) in the combination. A path in the ZDD ending at the 1-terminal node represents a variable combination (also known as ZDD minterm).

As an example, consider the circuit in Fig. 1(a) with its corresponding DAG in Fig. 1(b) and possible corresponding ZDDs in Fig. 2. A vertex v_i in the DAG in Fig. 1(b) corresponds to the circuit line i in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 shows two possible ZDDs for the DAG in Fig. 1(b), each using a different variable ordering. Both ZDDs have exactly 17 levels (one per DAG vertex). The ordering of the variables is shown on the left of each ZDD. A reverse topological order is used in Fig. 2(a) and a BFS-based order is used in Fig. 2(b). Dashed lines correspond to 0-edges and solid lines to 1-edges. The square nodes correspond to the root (top), 1-terminal, and 0-terminal nodes. A path starting at the root node and ending at the 1-terminal is a representation of a structural path in the circuit. For example, consider the shaded path of

Fig. 2(a) which corresponds to the path 4-9-10-12-14-16 marked by dashed lines in Fig. 1(a). The outgoing 0-edges from the ZDD nodes for variables v_{17} and v_7 in the shaded path indicate that lines 17 and 7 are off-path. The remaining off-path lines are implied as a suppressed node in a ZDD implies that the corresponding variable assumes the 0 value. Observe that, for the same path in a ZDD with different variable order (such as that in Fig. 2(b)) different variables may be suppressed or explicitly represented with outgoing 0-edges. In this particular example, variables v_1 , v_2 and v_3 are explicitly set to 0. A more detailed discussion on the impact of variable ordering in ZDDs is presented in Subsection 2.2.

The algorithm used to build the ZDD for all paths is presented in Section 3, and it utilizes standard ZDD operations to performed basic combinational set theoretic operations, such as Union, Intersection, etc. Table 1 lists the basic ZDD operations and functions used in this work as well as other relevant operations that can be used in applications of the proposed method. With Z_i we denote a ZDD and with r a ZDD variable.

For example, if ZDD_Union is applied between two ZDDs Z_1 and Z_2 , each representing a set of paths, a new set of paths is created which includes all the paths in either Z_1 , Z_2 , without any path duplication. Union is performed in a non-enumerative manner with respect to the paths. The same holds for many other set operations (including all listed in Table 1). This property makes ZDDs very attractive as several operations can be efficiently performed in time linear to the ZDD size.

The work of [25] proposed a more compact path representation compared to the one in [36]. Specifically, [25] shows that all paths can be represented using one ZDD variable per primary input and one ZDD variable per circuit branch line (referred to as *primary lines*). This approach is suitable for the PDF test grading problem and it constructs ZDDs with smaller size than those in [36]. However, since the entire paths are not kept in the structure, its applicability to other problems such that of [33] is not guaranteed. In Section 4 we consider both mappings (i.e, [36] and [25]) for rep-

Table 1 The basic ZDD operations.

ZDD Operation	Description
ZDD.Getnode(r, Z_1, Z_2)	searches for a set that consists of all combinations in Z_1 not containing variable r and all combinations in Z_2 containing variable r ; creates the set if not exist
ZDD.Change(Z, r)	augments combinations of Z with element r
ZDD.Union(Z_1, Z_2)	returns the union of all combinations in Z_1 and Z_2
ZDD.Difference(Z_1, Z_2)	removes all combinations of Z_2 from Z_1
ZDD.Intersect(Z_1, Z_2)	returns the intersection of all combinations in Z_1 and Z_2
ZDD.Count(Z)	returns the number of combinations in Z

Fig. 2 The representation of the paths of C17 considering: (a) reverse topological order (b) BFS-based order.

representing all structural paths and for PDF grading. In order to underline the generality of the proposed approach the remaining of this paper considers standard DAGs and, therefore, the complete path encoding of [36] is used.

2.2 The Variable Ordering Challenge

A known problem that limits the usage of Reduced Ordered Binary Decision Diagrams (BDDs) is their sensitivity on the variable ordering which can highly affect their size. ZDDs are not an exception to this. Fig. 2 illustrates the representation of all paths in the DAG of Fig. 1(b), using two different variable orders. Fig. 2(a) uses a variable ordering following a reverse topological order of the DAG’s vertices while Fig. 2(b) uses a Breadth First Search (BFS) order of the vertices (note that the labels of the vertices of the DAG follow a topological order). Although the two diagrams hold exactly the same paths, the representation in Fig. 2(a) is obviously more compact and, thus, more efficient. The reason for the increase of the ZDD size in Fig. 2(b) is attributed to the duplication of nodes for some variables, created in order to preserve the correctness of the representation. For example, there are three nodes for variables v_{12} and v_{16} and two nodes per variable v_7 and v_{10} . Nevertheless, note that there is a one-to-one correspondence between the ZDDs’ paths and the DAG’s

paths. The shaded paths in Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b) both represent the dashed path in the DAG in Fig. 1(b).

To ensure an efficient variable ordering for the construction of BDDs (and their variants), previous work has followed two different directions. *Static* approaches order the variable set prior to the construction of the BDD whereas *dynamic* approaches allow for ordering changes (re-ordering) during the construction of the BDD when specific conditions are met (e.g. size increase above a threshold).

Static ordering is in the general case less time and resource consuming and has been preferred for this in a number of previous works, [4,16] among many others. Due to their small computational effort static techniques are widely used and thoroughly explored. The work of [10] summarizes and compares some of the most effective static approaches.

On the other hand, dynamic approaches (also known as dynamic reordering) may lead to more efficient representations, where their application is not computationally prohibitive as their complexity is known to be NP-complete [5]. The numerous heuristics that follow the dynamic approach have been shown to work well for specific problems although they still remain resource demanding for large input instances [11,35,37,39]. Another reordering approach, mainly motivated by problems encountered in logic synthesis, tries to optimize the BDD size after its construction (see [13,15,20] among others). While many reordering approaches have been

previously proposed with considerable reduction in the size of the obtained BDD, they cannot control the size of the BDD during construction and may result in irreversible size increase. The comprehensive work of [14] summarizes these ordering approaches providing appropriate comparisons.

The BDD ordering techniques have been used in the vast majority of the works for ZDDs. The works in [21] and [24] attempt to incorporate concepts from BDD variable ordering to ZDDs, both specific to the problem they examine. None of these two methods provide an upper bound of the size of the obtained ZDD. Specifically, [21] proposes a good variable order for frequent itemsets used in data mining with very good improvements over the previously used approaches, yet its applicability is limited to the problem considered. The approach of [24] is also specific to the examined problem of *path delay fault coverage calculation* for digital circuits. As this work also uses the PDF coverage problem to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed theory, we have included appropriate discussion and experimentation in Section 4.

3 Path Representation using Linear Sized ZDDs

This section firstly describes the basic steps of the ZDD-based representation of the paths of a given DAG (Subsection 3.1). Then it presents reasoning proving that, when using the proposed variable order, the ZDD size is linear to the size of the initial DAG (Subsection 3.2). The proposed ordering for the variables of the ZDD to be constructed is taken based on the *reverse topological order of the DAG's vertices*. For the reverse topological order each vertex in the DAG has higher order than any of its predecessor vertices. The standard (not reverse) topological order can be used with the same *final* memory requirements (but not the same *peak* memory requirements). We propose the reverse topological order for two reasons: (a) the ZDD is constructed faster, and (b) the number of *intermediate* nodes is constant and smaller than the standard topological order.

3.1 All-path ZDD Construction

The proposed algorithm performs a topological traversal of the DAG and creates a ZDD per DAG vertex. The ZDD at a vertex represents all the path segments up to the vertex, starting from all vertices with no incoming edges (0 in-degree). The final ZDD is then obtained by unifying all ZDDs of the ending vertices (0 out-degree) into a single ZDD.

```
construct_paths_ZDD(G)
```

Inputs: Directed Acyclic Graph $G(V, E)$

Output: ZDD P representing all paths of G

01: $R = \text{create } |V| \text{ ZDD variables, one } \forall v \in V : r_i \rightarrow v_i$

02: $R^{ord} = \text{order_variables}(R, \text{order_method})$

03: $V^{ord} = \text{order_DAG}(V, \text{topological_order})$

04: ZDD $P = \emptyset$

05: **for each** vertex $v_i \in V^{ord}, i=1, 2, \dots, |V|$

06: ZDD $Z_i = \emptyset$

07: **for each** vertex $v_j \in V^{ord}, j=1, 2, \dots, |V| : \text{edge } e_{j,i} \in E$

08: $Z_i = \text{ZDD_Union}(Z_i, Z_j)$

09: $Z_i = \text{ZDD_Change}(Z_i, r_i), r_i \in R^{ord}$

10: % Collect paths from all vertices with no successors

11: **for each** vertex $v_i \in V^{ord} : \text{out_degree}(v_i) = 0$

12: $P = \text{ZDD_Union}(P, Z_i)$

13: **return** P

Fig. 3 ZDD construction for representing all paths in a DAG.

The algorithm given in Fig. 3 outlines the basic steps of the all-path construction algorithm we use in this work. The algorithm follows similar principles as those used in [36] which constructs logical paths instead of structural paths which are considered here. While a structural path refers only to the sequence of interconnection lines in a circuit, a logical path refers to a structural path with a logic value transition (rising or falling) initiated at the path's source (primary input). A PDF models a delayed propagation of the transition of the logical path. The algorithm input is a DAG with its set of vertices V and its set of edges E . In lines 01-02 one ZDD variable per DAG edge is created and all variables are ordered statically. Then, the DAG is traversed in a topological manner and a ZDD is formed at each vertex using two basic ZDD operations i.e., ZDD_Union and ZDD_Change (lines 03-09). Traversing the DAG topologically is crucial in order to ensure that each vertex is processed after all its predecessors have been processed. This can be implemented either in a dynamic fashion using queues or following a static pre-sorting of the DAG's vertices (line 03). To distinguish between a DAG vertex and its corresponding ZDD variable, we denote the former by v_i and the latter by r_i . For each vertex v_i a ZDD Z_i is constructed to hold all the path segments from the source vertices to v_i . Source vertices refer to vertices with 0 in-degree in the DAG. Z_i is built by applying the standard iterative two-way ZDD_Union() operation across all ZDDs corresponding to the immediate predecessors of v_i (lines 07-08) plus a ZDD_Change() operation (line 09) in order to add the variable r_i corresponding to v_i in Z_i . By ZDD_Change(Z_i, r_i) (line 09) each path contained in Z_i is augmented with a variable corresponding to vertex v_i , i.e., r_i . This step terminates when all vertices have been processed. The final ZDD P holding all

paths in the DAG is constructed by taking the union of all Z_i corresponding to sink vertices (lines 11-12), i.e., vertices with 0 out-degree.

When the underlying DAG represents a combinational circuit netlist, the size of the all-paths ZDD can be optimized by reducing the number of ZDD variables; vertices corresponding to branch lines in the circuit can be excluded from the encoding without any impact on the correctness of the representation. Furthermore, when using ZDDs for the PDF fault grading problem, the algorithm in Fig. 3 can be easily modified to consider the mapping of [25] which uses ZDD variables only for primary input and branch lines. Our analysis in the next subsection on the number of necessary ZDD nodes is given based on the generated encoding of the paths using distinct ZDD variables for each vertex in the DAG, and it holds for both the aforementioned variable optimization encodings.

3.2 Optimality of the Proposed Variable Ordering for Linear-sized All-Path ZDDs.

In the rest of this section we show that the algorithm in Fig. 3 produces a ZDD of linear size with respect to the size of the DAG whose paths are to be represented. To show this, we provide analytical evidence that the basic ZDD operations used in the process of Fig. 3 do not increase the ZDD size (in terms of nodes) beyond the DAG size plus one, when its variable ordering follows a reverse topological order on the DAG vertices. The optimality of the proposed ordering is then proven based on the observation that each DAG vertex is processed only once.

Before discussing the proof, we present the outline of the two basic ZDD operations considered here, in Fig. 4 together with the ZDD_Getnode() operation necessary for the realization of the other two. At this point it is necessary to clarify the difference between a ZDD variable and a ZDD node. A node is a vertex with two possible children (one reached via the 0-edge and one via the 1-edge). A node corresponds to a ZDD variable which represents a problem's attribute, in our case a DAG's vertex. While there is a one-to-one relationship between a ZDD variable and a DAG vertex, there is a many-to-one relationship between a ZDD node and a ZDD variable. In other words, there may be more than one nodes corresponding to the same variable (siblings) since each sibling's children may be different. For the operations in Fig. 4, $P.top$ refers to the top node of ZDD P ; P_0 and P_1 point to the subdiagrams with root at the 0-edge and 1-edge children nodes of P , respectively. Comparisons are done considering the variable

```

ZDD_Getnode( $top, P_0, P_1$ )
if ( $P_1 == \emptyset$ ) return  $P_0$ ; % node elimination
 $P$  = search a node with ( $top, P_0, P_1$ ) in unique-table;
if ( $P$  exist) return  $P$ ; % node sharing
 $P$  = generate a node with ( $top, P_0, P_1$ );
append  $P$  to the unique-table;
return  $P$ ;

```

(a)

```

ZDD_Change( $P, var$ )
if ( $P.top > var$ ) return Getnode( $var, \emptyset, P$ );
if ( $P.top == var$ ) return Getnode( $var, P_0, P_1$ );
if ( $P.top < var$ )
  return Getnode( $P.top, Change(P_0, var), Change(P_1, var)$ );

```

(b)

```

ZDD_Union( $P, Q$ )
if ( $P == \emptyset$ ) return  $Q$ ;
if ( $Q == \emptyset$ ) return  $P$ ;
if ( $P == Q$ ) return  $P$ ;
if ( $P.top < Q.top$ )
  return Getnode( $P.top, Union(P_0, Q), P_1$ );
if ( $P.top > Q.top$ )
  return Getnode( $Q.top, Union(P, Q_0), Q_1$ );
if ( $P.top == Q.top$ )
  return Getnode( $P.top, Union(P_0, Q_0), Union(P_1, Q_1)$ );

```

(c)

Fig. 4 Standard ZDD Union and Change operations ([31]).

ordering (e.g., $P.top > var$ means that the variable corresponding to node $P.top$ is of higher order than var). A ZDD node with higher order appears below nodes with lower order in the diagram¹. We begin the proof with some observations from the algorithms in Fig. 4.

Definition 1 A path in a DAG $G(V, E)$ is a combination of consecutive edges $p \subset E$ starting from a vertex $s \in V$ and ending at a vertex $d \in V$ such that s has 0 in-degree and d has 0 out-degree.

Corollary 1 The ZDD representing all paths (according to Definition 1) in a DAG is constructed by traversing the graph following a topological order on its vertices (line 04 of the algorithm of Fig. 3).

Corollary 2 During the path construction process, a ZDD_Change() operation is called exactly once for each variable of the ZDD (line 09 of the algorithm of Fig. 3).

Definition 2 A reverse topological order of the variables of a ZDD representing a DAG's paths is a

¹ This definition of the variable order is in accordance with the one proposed in [6] where Ordered BDDs were introduced, and is the one mostly used in the related literature. The work of [31] uses a definition for the variable order in the completely opposite fashion, i.e., nodes with higher order appear above nodes with lower order. While this does not affect the nature of the proposed work, we have changed the procedures of Fig. 4 to follow the most common definition, as in [6].

numbering of the ZDD variables obtained by following a topological visiting of the DAG's vertices where each variable is numbered in a decreasing order as the vertices are visited.

Considering the DAG in Fig. 1(b), a topological visit traverses the DAG in the (possible) order $v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8, v_9, v_{10}, v_{11}, v_{12}, v_{13}, v_{14}, v_{15}, v_{16}, v_{17}$ and the corresponding reverse topological order of the variables is defined as $r_{17}, r_{16}, r_{15}, r_{14}, r_{13}, r_{12}, r_{11}, r_{10}, r_9, r_8, r_7, r_6, r_5, r_4, r_3, r_2, r_1$ following the convention used in the algorithm in Fig. 3.

The `ZDD_Getnode()` operation (described in Fig. 4(a)) accepts as inputs a **variable** top and two sub-graphs P_0 and P_1 . It returns a **node** P corresponding to top and with P_0 and P_1 connected to its 0-edge and 1-edge, respectively. All nodes are kept to a structure called *unique table* where no node (corresponding to the same variable with the same children) exists twice. Analyzing the `ZDD_Getnode()` operation we identify two possibilities: (i) such a ZDD node exists, no new node is created and P is identical to that node, and (ii) such ZDD node does not exist and P is created and added to the unique table.

Corollary 3 *A single call of `ZDD_Getnode(top, P0, P1)` function can create at most one new node for variable top . A new node is constructed if and only if there exists no node in the unique table corresponding to top having its 0-edge and 1-edge pointing to P_0 and P_1 , respectively.*

Lemma 1 *The `ZDD_Change(Zi, ri)` operation at line 09 of process in Fig. 3 adds exactly one new node to ZDD Z_i which corresponds to variable r_i when the ZDD variables are ordered in a reverse topological order.*

Proof Let $Z_i = P$ and $r_i = var$ based on the description of Fig. 4(b). `ZDD_Change(P, var)` augments all paths of ZDD P with variable var . This implies that, if necessary, more than one nodes may be created to ensure the ZDD's canonical attribute. However, a call of `ZDD_Change()` occurs only once (Corollary 2) and only when all DAG vertices with lower topological order have been visited (Corollary 1). From Definition 2, all variables in P have higher topological order than var . This case falls under the first condition of the `ZDD_Change()` operation that calls a `ZDD_Getnode()` operation once to create or return a node corresponding to var . No such node exists in the unique table because `ZDD_Getnode()` is called for the first time for var and, thus, from Corollary 3, it follows that exactly one node is created. From the latter and since a single `ZDD_Getnode()` is called for each `ZDD_Change()` which in turn is called once per ZDD variable, the lemma follows.

In practice, the variable augmentation is achieved by placing the node corresponding to variable var on top of all variables of ZDD P . Since, by definition, all the paths of P pass (originate) from the root node of a ZDD, placing the new node above the root adds var to all paths of P . A different variable ordering where the order of var was somewhere in between the root and the terminal nodes could have enforced the duplication of var (creation of more nodes corresponding to var) in order to make sure that all the paths include var . We illustrate this case in Fig. 5. In Fig. 5(b) the new variable (var) has lower order than the top node ($r_8 < r_9$) and, hence, it is placed on top of the existing ZDD (initially shown in Fig. 5(a)) connected through its 1-edge to the existing ZDD (P) and through its 0-edge to the 0-terminal node, without disturbing the existing structure. This is exactly what happens in every call of `ZDD_Change()` when the ZDD variables are ordered in the proposed ordering. On the contrary, in Fig. 5(c) the new variable has higher order than the top node of the ZDD ($r_{11} > r_9$). In order to preserve the correct ordering of the variables (the new variable should be placed between levels r_{10} and r_{12}), two new nodes are created corresponding to variable r_{11} , shown in the dashed ellipse. This case is very usual in variable ordering other than the proposed and is the reason for the large size of the ZDDs shown in Section 4 for the other orderings considered. For the standard (not reverse) topological variable ordering, the new variable should be placed on the lowest level (just above 1-terminal node). While this will eventually add only a single node to the ZDD, the recursive approach of `ZDD_Change()` (last line in Fig. 4(b)) will significantly affect the runtime of this step and, consequently, of the entire approach.

Corollary 4 *When the algorithm of Fig. 3 uses the reverse topological variable order, the `ZDD_Change(Zi, ri)` operation augments all paths of Z_i with variable r_i by placing the corresponding node on the top of Z_i and connecting its 1-edge to Z_i and its 0-edge to the 0-terminal node.*

The `ZDD_Union()` operation takes as operands two ZDD P and Q and gives as output a ZDD containing all unique paths in P and Q . Observe that, `ZDD_Union()` is a recursive process where the `ZDD_Getnode()` function can be called at most $|P|+|Q|$ times. Thus, the number of new nodes to be created by a `ZDD_Union()` operation can be equal to the sum of the nodes of the two operand ZDDs. We show that, not only this upper bound is not reached, but for the process of Fig 3 no extra node is created when $Z_i = \text{ZDD_Union}(Z_i, Z_j)$ (line 08) is executed.

Fig. 5 An example of the `ZDD.Change()` step. Variables corresponding to each node is shown on the left of each diagram. (a) Diagram before the `ZDD.Change()` application. (b) The new variable has lower order than the root of the ZDD. (c) The new variable has higher order than the root of the ZDD.

Lemma 2 The $Z_i = \text{ZDD_Union}(Z_i, Z_j)$ operation in line 08 of the process in Fig. 3 does not create any new ZDD nodes when its variables are ordered in a reverse topological order.

Proof Let $Z_i = P$ and $Z_j = Q$ based on the description of Fig. 4(c). Without loss of generality, let the outcome of the `ZDD_Union()` be assigned to a ZDD other than Z_i , let that be F . Analyzing the process in Fig. 4(c) we identify 6 different cases based on the relationship between P and Q each of which corresponds to a line in the corresponding pseudocode. The lemma holds for the first three cases, i.e., P or Q equal to zero and $P = Q$ in a straightforward manner as it returns existing ZDDs (either P or Q) which ensures no new node is created. The last case ($P.\text{top} == Q.\text{top}$) implies at least two nodes corresponding to the same variable. Since from Lemma 1 the `ZDD.Change()` operation creates exactly one node each time it is called and because it is called only once for each DAG vertex (Corollary 2), we will consider this case only if the remaining two cases can create multiple nodes per variable. The two remaining cases ($P.\text{top} < Q.\text{top}$ and $P.\text{top} > Q.\text{top}$) are symmetrical and, thus, without loss of generality we consider only the first. Both P and Q have been created by a prior call of the `ZDD.Change()` operation and, hence, from Corollary 4 P_0 and Q_0 point to the 0-terminal node. Thus, the call of `ZDD_Getnode()` returns F with root node 1 and 3-6 (line 08 in Fig. 3). After this `ZDD_Union()` step (`ZDD` shown in bold) a new node $n6.2$ for vari-

connected to its 1-edge and Q connected to its 0-edge. The latter occurs because the inline `ZDD_Union()` operation returns Q since $P_0 = 0$ (case $P == 0$). F has exactly the same number of nodes as that in both P and Q , with its new node $F.\text{top}$ replacing $P.\text{top}$ and corresponding exactly to the same variable. According to the path construction process (Fig. 3) a `ZDD_Union()` operation takes place at the incoming edges of a DAG's vertex. By definition, $P.\text{top}$ can only correspond to the incoming edges of one vertex (that corresponding to F). Hence, $P.\text{top}$ will never be used again in the remaining steps of the process and can be immediately deleted from the unique table. Therefore, the size of the unique table is not changed because of the `ZDD_Union()` call, and the lemma follows.

We illustrate this step with an example (Fig. 6) considering the DAG in Fig. 1(b). The example demonstrates the execution of the process for the construction of the path segments up to vertex v_8 . “Line 3” and “Line 1” correspond to ZDDs for the two source vertices v_3 and v_1 , respectively. When vertex v_6 is to be added, a `ZDD.Change()` operation is applied giving the ZDD named “Sub 3-6”. Next, a `ZDD_Union()` is applied between ZDDs “Line 1” and “Sub 3-6” in order to construct a new ZDD that holds both path segments (line 08 in Fig. 3). After this `ZDD_Union()` step (`ZDD` shown in bold) a new node $n6.2$ for vari-

able r_6 is created in order to accommodate these two path segments and keep 3-6 intact for further reference. However, 3-6 will not be used by the ZDD construction algorithm in the following iterations (only used for circuit line 8), and $n6.1$ can, hence, be released. Indeed, the next `ZDD.Change()` adds a new node $n8$ for vertex v_8 which is connected to the new node for variable r_6 ($n6.2$) and contains the correct path segments to be augmented with v_8 . ZDD “Sub 1-8, 3-6-8” contains path segments 1-8 and 3-6-8.

So, as an intermediate result, the process may produce an extra node after a pairwise `ZDD.Union()` which, however, can be immediately discarded. In the case where all edges of the DAG correspond to primary lines (source vertices and vertices with out-degree > 1) as described in [26], the number of these intermediate nodes is two. The reason is because both P and Q have 0-edge that do not point to the terminal 0 as they have not been created using a `ZDD.Change()` but a `ZDD.Union()` operation instead. The proof for this is similar to that of Lemma 2.

The following two lemmata refer to the last step of the process of Fig. 3 (lines 11-12) which merges the ZDDs of the vertices of the DAG with 0 out-degree.

Lemma 3 *The iterative calls of `ZDD.Union()` in line 12 of the process of Fig. 3 are performed along DAG vertices that can be sorted in a monotonically descending order of their corresponding ZDD variables.*

Proof The calls of the `ZDD.Union()` are done along vertices of the DAG with 0 out-degree. Since these vertices are not connected to each other and by definition of the topological order, their relative order does not disturb the topological order. Hence, the order of the

Fig. 6 An example of a `ZDD.Union()` step followed by a `ZDD.Change()`.

corresponding variables can be arbitrary and, thus, can be chosen to be a descending one with respect to the order that the vertices are visited. Since, no two vertices of the DAG can correspond to the same ZDD variable this order is also monotonic and the lemma follows.

Lemma 4 *The iterative calls of `ZDD.Union(P, Z_i)` in lines 11-12 of the process of Fig. 3 do not create new ZDD nodes.*

Proof According to Lemma 3 the top node of Z_i has lower order than the top node of P since P has been constructed at a previous iteration of the loop which iterates along the ZDDs corresponding to 0 out-degree vertices of the DAG. This implies that for each such call of the `ZDD.Union()` operation $P.top > Z_i.top$ (fifth case in the Fig. 4(c)). The call of `ZDD.Union()` within the `ZDD.Getnode()` returns P since Z_{i0} was constructed with a `ZDD.Change()` operation and from Corollary 4 points to the 0-terminal node. Hence, `ZDD.Union()` returns a new ZDD, let that be R with $R.top$ corresponding to the variable of $Z_i.top$, $R_0 = P$ and $R_1 = Z_{i1}$. $R.top$ is a new node corresponding to the variable of $Z_i.top$ and pointing to existing nodes i.e., P and Z_{i1} . Similarly to Lemma 2, $R.top$ can fully replace $Z_i.top$ in the unique table since $Z_i.top$ will never be used in the future and, since its children are existing nodes, the lemma follows.

Summarizing the observations above we can now conclude on the size of the ZDD constructed by the path representation process by considering the proposed reverse topological order on the ZDD variables.

Theorem 1 *When a ZDD representing all paths in a DAG is constructed using a topological traversal on the DAG’s vertices (as shown in Fig. 3) and under a reverse topological variable order, the resulting ZDD has exactly the same number of nodes as the vertices in the DAG.*

Proof The path construction process of Fig. 3 uses a topological traversal on the DAG vertices (Corollary 1) and its only two steps that manipulate a ZDD uses the `ZDD.Union()` and `ZDD.Change()` operations of Fig. 4. From Corollary 2 a `ZDD.Change()` operation is called one time for each DAG vertex and from Lemma 1 each such call creates exactly one new ZDD node. According to Lemma 2, `ZDD.Union()` creates a new ZDD node that can immediately replace another node that corresponds to the same DAG vertex. From Lemma 4, the final iterative call of the `ZDD.Union()` on the vertices of the DAG with 0 out-degree does not add any new nodes to the ZDD. Thus, in the final ZDD exactly one node per DAG vertex exists and the theorem follows.

Table 2 Number of ZDD nodes required to represent all paths using different orderings.

circuit	# paths	# DAG vertices	number of ZDD nodes (peak)				ZDD nodes increase wrt reverse topological		
			reverse topological	topological	BFS	random	topological	BFS	random
s38584	1080721	38582	38582	38582	257815	7542862	1x	7x	196x
c5315	1341305	5315	5315	5315	143597	11578654	1x	27x	2178x
s13207	1345319	13157	13157	13157	154256	10038921	1x	12x	763x
s38417	1391439	38277	38277	38277	487782	18940627	1x	13x	495x
mem_ctr	1696107	36170	36170	36170	1637296	122465529	1x	45x	3386x
ethernet	1920487	223959	223959	223959	*	*	1x	*	*
c1355	4173216	1355	1355	1355	140428	19124586	1x	104x	14114x
c3540	28676671	3540	3540	3540	180590	110984532	1x	51x	31352x
b14	93392489	21678	21678	21678	2522449	101154201	1x	116x	4666x
b21	149382311	31157	31157	31157	6354418	*	1x	204x	*
s15850	164738035	15839	15839	15839	294154172	*	1x	18572x	*
tv80	207757182	24357	24357	24357	499601938	*	1x	20512x	*
b20	289792088	43375	43375	43375	*	*	1x	*	*
b22	437362328	64401	64401	64401	*	*	1x	*	*
systemcaes	472885123	30012	30012	30012	1200309	19851145	1x	40x	661x
b15	48255845600	20186	20186	20186	*	*	1x	*	*
b17	3.95339×10^{11}	71511	71511	71511	*	*	1x	*	*
c6288	9.89434×10^{19}	6288	6288	6288	26307302	12064710	1x	4184x	1919x
b18	1.13124×10^{24}	237235	237235	*	*	*	*	*	*

Table 3 CPU time required to represent all paths using different orderings.

circuit	# paths	# DAG vertices	CPU time (secs)				CPU time increase wrt to rev. topological		
			reverse topological	topological	BFS	random	topological	BFS	random
s38584	1080721	38582	1.28	213.49	524.71	681.09	167x	410x	532x
c5315	1341305	5315	0.04	2.05	11.22	14.39	51x	281x	360x
s13207	1345319	13157	0.23	76.32	88.27	88.41	332x	384x	384x
s38417	1391439	38277	0.45	232.17	689.25	583.32	516x	1532x	1296x
mem_ctr	1696107	36170	0.66	272.66	518.23	697.16	413x	785x	1056x
ethernet	1920487	223959	86.75	6952.21	>18h	>18h	80x	>747x	>747x
c1355	4173216	1355	0.01	0.57	1.16	2.96	57x	116x	296x
c3540	28676671	3540	0.03	3.52	7.41	20.71	117x	247x	690x
b14	93392489	21678	0.17	259.65	337.6	758.62	1527x	1986x	4462x
b21	149382311	31157	0.3	486.11	965.33	>18h	1620x	3218x	>216000x
s15850	164738035	15839	0.21	148.31	923.7	>18h	706x	4399x	>308571x
tv80	207757182	24357	0.24	316.29	1627	>18h	1318x	6779x	>270000x
b20	289792088	43375	0.39	927.29	>18h	>18h	2378x	>166154x	>166154x
b22	437362328	64401	0.69	1914.81	>18h	>18h	2775x	>93913x	>93913x
systemcaes	472885123	30012	0.46	348.29	422.57	579.36	757x	919x	1259x
b15	48255845600	20186	0.23	235.84	>18h	>18h	1025x	>281739x	>281739x
b17	3.95339×10^{11}	71511	1.91	2796.12	>18h	>18h	1464x	>33927x	>33927x
c6288	9.89434×10^{19}	6288	0.04	15.5	28.4	296.21	388x	710x	7405x
b18	1.13124×10^{24}	237235	12.45	>18h	>18h	>18h	>5205x	>5205x	>5205x

4 Experimental Results

The proposed method was implemented in C++ language using the decision diagram package of [43] (for all ZDD related operations), and run on a 64-bit 1GHZ SunBlade 2500 workstation with 32GB of memory. For all the experiments, the DAGs considered were derived from the netlists of the digital circuits in the IWLS benchmark suite. We report results only for circuits with more than one million paths.

Table 2 reports results when all the structural paths of each circuit considered are represented using a single ZDD. The process of Fig. 3 has been used considering the mapping in [36]. Column 2 reports the number of paths in the circuit as obtained by the ZDD structure. These numbers are very easily obtained since counting the number of paths in a ZDD is linear to its size. Column 3 lists the number of DAG vertices, which correspond to the number of circuit lines. Column 4 reports the number of peak ZDD nodes for the representation, when the proposed reverse topological order of the ZDD variables is used. Column 5 reports the respective numbers when the topological order is used, instead. As ex-

pected, for all circuits examined the numbers reported for both these orderings are equal to the number of the DAG vertices as proven in Subsection 3.2. Recall that while the two orders require the same number of nodes for the representation, the latter requires significantly more time (see also the results in Table 3). Columns 6 and 7 report the number of nodes required under a BFS order and a random order of the ZDD variables, respectively. Columns 8, 9, and 10 report the increase on the size of the ZDD (compared to the proposed order) for the three alternative static ordering methods. Obviously, the topological orders are by far the best options. Entries marked with * represent cases that the execution has been terminated after 18 hours. This termination condition also affects the case of using a topological traversal for benchmark b18. Although, theoretically the size of the ZDD is equal to that of the proposed order, it could not be verified experimentally as the execution time exceeded the pre-defined threshold of 18 hours.

Table 3 reports the corresponding CPU time (in seconds) needed for the path representation using ZDDs for the same circuits and variable orderings (Columns

Table 4 Number of ZDD nodes required to represent all paths using different initial orderings with dynamic reordering enabled.

circuit	# paths	# DAG vertices	number of ZDD nodes (peak)				ZDD node decrease wrt static ordering			
			reverse topological	topological	BFS	random	reverse topological	topological	BFS	random
s38584	1080721	38582	38582	40975	102766	254318	1.00x	1.06x	0.40x	0.03x
c5315	1341305	5315	5315	5315	122365	133034	1.00x	1.00x	0.85x	0.01x
s13207	1345319	13157	13157	13948	121463	8325699	1.00x	1.06x	0.79x	0.83x
s38417	1391439	38277	38277	42570	419545	13125631	1.00x	1.11x	0.86x	0.69x
mem_ctr	1696107	36170	36170	40083	1071962	99844318	1.00x	1.11x	0.65x	0.82x
ethernet	1920487	223959	223959	*	*	*	1.00x	*	*	*
c1355	4173216	1355	1355	2132	1355	1390942	1.00x	1.57x	0.01x	0.07x
c3540	28676671	3540	3540	3540	90487	71164328	1.00x	1.00x	0.50x	0.64x
b14	93392489	21678	21678	30272	1924585	44521654	1.00x	1.40x	0.76x	0.44x
b21	149382311	31157	31157	41720	*	*	1.00x	1.34x	*	*
s15850	164738035	15839	15839	18057	49161045	*	1.00x	1.14x	0.17x	*
tv80	207757182	24357	24357	30664	551419904	*	1.00x	1.26x	1.10x	*
b20	289792088	43375	43375	51869	*	*	1.00x	1.20x	*	*
b22	437362328	64401	64401	64401	*	*	1.00x	1.00x	*	*
systemcaes	472885123	30012	30012	34846	862158	*	1.00x	1.16x	0.72x	*
b15	48255845600	20186	20186	28360	*	*	1.00x	1.40x	*	*
b17	3.95339×10^{11}	71511	71511	71511	*	*	1.00x	1.00x	*	*
c6288	9.89434×10^{19}	6288	6288	12314	6288	152166	1.00x	1.96x	0.0002x	0.01x
b18	1.13124×10^{24}	237235	237235	*	*	*	1.00x	*	*	*

Table 5 CPU time required to represent all paths using different initial orderings with dynamic reordering enabled.

circuit	# paths	# DAG vertices	CPU time (secs)				CPU time increase wrt static ordering			
			reverse topological	topological	BFS	random	reverse topological	topological	BFS	random
s38584	1080721	38582	2.43	479.87	932.87	1279.48	1.90x	2.25x	1.78x	1.88x
c5315	1341305	5315	0.06	3.61	20.08	21.67	1.50x	1.76x	1.79x	1.51x
s13207	1345319	13157	0.53	129.78	134.52	135.82	2.30x	1.70x	1.52x	1.54x
s38417	1391439	38277	0.99	374.13	1065.57	1296.19	2.20x	1.61x	1.55x	2.22x
mem_ctr	1696107	36170	1.48	918.29	1251.97	1195.51	2.24x	3.37x	2.42x	1.71x
ethernet	1920487	223959	90.82	> 18h	> 18h	> 18h	1.05x	*	*	*
c1355	4173216	1355	0.01	1.12	2.13	5.08	1.00x	1.96x	1.84x	1.72x
c3540	28676671	3540	0.04	5.99	12.34	39.15	1.33x	1.70x	1.67x	1.89x
b14	93392489	21678	0.33	386.06	507.06	1220.85	1.94x	1.49x	1.50x	1.61x
b21	149382311	31157	0.3	849.73	>18h	>18h	1.00x	1.75x	*	*
s15850	164738035	15839	0.46	207.03	1107.44	>18h	2.19x	1.40x	1.20x	*
tv80	207757182	24357	0.43	483.09	1752.13	> 18h	1.79x	1.53x	1.08x	*
b20	289792088	43375	0.7	1773.31	>18h	>18h	1.79x	1.91x	*	*
b22	437362328	64401	1.45	>18h	>18h	>18h	2.10x	*	*	*
systemcaes	472885123	30012	0.98	461.82	546.55	730.67	2.13x	1.33x	1.29x	1.26x
b15	48255845600	20186	0.49	378.52	>18h	>18h	2.13x	1.60x	*	*
b17	3.95339×10^{11}	71511	2.34	4850.27	>18h	>18h	1.23x	1.73x	*	*
c6288	9.89434×10^{19}	6288	0.07	23.06	41.63	985.11	1.75x	1.49x	1.47x	3.33x
b18	1.13124×10^{24}	237235	19.35	>18h	>18h	>18h	1.55x	*	*	*

4, 5, 6 and 7) as those in Table 2. Columns 8, 9 and 10 list the relevant increases in CPU time. The main observation is that for all ordering methods the algorithm needs considerable time to execute except for the reverse topological ordering. Even for the standard topological ordering where the size of the ZDD is the same as in the case of the reverse topological ordering, the execution time becomes much higher (on average 2800x slower). The reason is that for the reverse topological order the new node is placed on top of the existing ZDD while for the standard topological order the new node has to traverse the entire diagram (from its root to the 1-terminal node) in order to be consistent with the ordered considered. Subsection 3.2 provides the detailed explanation and an example after Lemma 1. Although not prohibitive for several cases, using the standard topological ordering has no benefit at all over using the reverse topological one.

Since previous works on BDD variable ordering suggest the usage of dynamic reordering techniques to cope

with the size of the diagram, we investigate whether a dynamic reordering of the variables [11,35,37,39] may help in canceling the high memory/time requirements of the other ordering methods. While in Subsection 3.2 we have given a theoretical proof of the optimality of the proposed ordering, successful dynamic reordering of the variables could potentially weaken its impact. Since all the previously proposed dynamic reordering techniques are heuristics, we approach this issue experimentally.

Tables 4 and 5 report the same results as Tables 2 and 3 respectively, but this time with dynamic reordering enabled. For this experimentation the popular dynamic reordering technique of [39] is used as implemented in the CUDD package [43]. Columns 4,5,6 and 7 report the resource requirements (peak ZDD nodes in Table 4 and CPU times in Table 5) when dynamic reordering is enabled. The initial variable ordering in each case follows the static ordering considered in the previous tables. Columns 8, 9, 10 and 11 report the decrease in peak ZDD nodes for each case, when com-

pared to the required peak nodes of the static ordering approaches (columns 4-7 of Table 2). For example, consider circuit s38584. When dynamic reordering is enabled the node count for the BFS ordering is reduced to 0.4x of the nodes required when a purely static ordering approach is used. This is calculated by comparing the 257815 nodes required when BFS ordering is applied without dynamic reordering enabled (Column 6 of Table 2) with the 102766 nodes required when dynamic reordering was enabled (Column 6 of Table 4). Of course this is done in the expense of CPU time which is increased by 78% (Column 9 of Table 5) with respect to the BFS ordering without the dynamic reordering. Entries with * denote that the comparison is not possible as the execution takes excessive CPU time, meeting the termination condition of 18 hours.

The obvious finding from this investigation is that dynamic reordering increases the execution times considerably. In all reported cases the execution time is higher than the time required for the corresponding static variable ordering approaches. For the BFS and Random orderings the node counts are decreased, for some cases significantly, with dynamic reordering. This shows effective exploitation of the extra CPU time, although in all cases the obtained node counts are much higher than those obtained using the proposed optimal static reverse topological order. For example, for s38584, the node count using the random variable ordering is 33 times smaller when dynamic reordering is enabled. Nevertheless, this gives a peak node count of 254318 which is 6.6 times larger than the node count when the reverse topological order is used without dynamic reordering. Dynamic reordering manages to match the optimal order only for circuits c1355 and c6288, when an initial BFS order is used. Note that dynamic reordering increases the CPU time even in the case of the optimal ordering which is attributed to the extra condition checks performed by dynamic reordering (even when no reordering is actually performed). Finally, dynamic reordering negatively affects the standard topological ordering for both metrics. While the CPU time needed is increased as in all cases, the node count does not decrease, on the contrary, in many cases it increases considerably.

5 Application to Path Delay Fault Grading

Previous work on path representation in digital circuits has been developed in relation to the Path Delay Fault (PDF) model [42], where a fault is a logical circuit path modeled as a delayed transition across a structural path. Several related problems have been inves-

tigated, for the PDF model including PDF simulation (or grading) [2, 17, 24, 28, 36, 41].

Path enumerative methods are inherently problematic for this problem due to the large number of paths in a circuit, while the early non-enumerative methods give only a pessimistic estimation of the fault coverage [2]. The first work that proposed an exact methodology for PDF fault coverage calculation used a special data structure called path-status graph [17]. This data structure can become of exponential size with respect to the size of the circuit considered. [36] also proposed an exact algorithm using ZDDs. While the latter method can, in the worst case, result in an exponentially large structure, in practice ZDDs have been shown to cope well when representing paths. A preliminary experimental study investigating the size of ZDDs when representing paths under different ZDD variable orderings was performed in [24]. Yet, none of the existing works addresses the complexity and optimality of the variable ordering.

In this section we consider the PDF grading problem i.e., the exact calculation of the fault coverage of a test set with respect to the PDF model, when ZDDs are used under the proposed optimal variable ordering. For every structural path 2 PDFs are modeled, one with a rising and one with a falling transition in the path's input. A valid test for a PDF is a pair of input vectors (t_1, t_2) that excites the associated transition at the first node of the PDF (primary input or scan chain element) and allows its propagation to an observable point (either primary output or scan chain element). Tests may consider different sensitization conditions for the circuit lines affecting the propagation, namely the lines that are *side inputs* to the gates and are not on the considered path. As an example of the problem and its representation using ZDDs consider Fig. 7. In Fig. 7(a) the simulation of test P1=(01101, 01111) is shown. 3 PDFs (indicated with dashed lines) are detected i.e., $\{4R - 9 - 10 - 12 - 14 - 16, 4R - 9 - 10 - 12 - 15 - 17, 4R - 9 - 11 - 13 - 17\}$. $s0(s1)$ indicates that the corresponding line remains stable at 0(1) during the application of P1. $4R$ indicates a rising transition in line 4 and implies the corresponding transitions across the path e.g., $4R - 9 - 10 - 12 - 14 - 16$ implies a rising transition on lines 12 and 14 and a falling transition on lines 9, 10, and 16. The 3 PDFs detected by P1 are represented by the ZDD in Fig. 7(c) in a similar manner as the structural path representation described in Section 2.1. Note, however, that for the PDF grading problem 2 variables are defined per primary input, one for each transition. Fig. 7(b) shows the application of test P2=(01010, 00010) detecting paths $\{2F - 12 - 14 - 16, 2F - 12 - 15 - 17\}$. The corresponding ZDD is shown in Fig. 7(d). The diagram of

Fig. 7 Constructing a ZDD for Path Delay Fault grading calculation. (a) Application of Test Vector Pair P1, (b) Application of Test Vector Pair P2, (c) PDFs tested by P1, (d) PDFs tested by P2, (e) PDFs tested by both P1 and P2.

Fig. 7(e) contains all PDFs detected by both P1 and P2, and has been obtained by a standard `ZDD_Union()` operation between the ZDDs of Fig. 7(c) and (d). Following this rationale, a ZDD Z_{det} is constructed holding all PDFs detected by all vector pairs in the test set. Due to the canonical property of ZDDs, PDFs detected by more than one tests are represented only once in Z_{det} . The number of PDFs in Z_{det} can be obtained in time linear to its size with a single traversal from its root to the 1-terminal node. A ZDD Z_{all} to hold all the PDFs in a circuit netlist can be constructed following the algorithm of Fig. 3. The PDF fault coverage of a given test set is computed by dividing the number of PDFs (minterms) in Z_{det} by the number of PDFs in Z_{all} . For the example in Fig. 7, as there are 18 possible PDFs in Z_{all} (9 rising plus 9 falling PDFs in the example cir-

cuit), and 5 detected PDFs in the ZDD in Fig. 7(e), the coverage for the test set $\{P1, P2\}$ is $5/18$. The interested reader is referred to the work of [36] for a detailed description and analysis of this methodology, which is not the purpose of this work.

Next, we show results related to the PDF test grading problem, as outlined above. In order to fully exercise the capabilities and the possible limitations of the proposed variable ordering we consider (as in [25]) the representation of all possible PDFs in a circuit i.e. achieving 100% fault coverage (existing test sets report smaller coverage)². **Thus, in this experimentation**

² We have chosen to compare with [25] instead of the same authors' previous work in [24] which proposes a specific variable ordering, as the results in [25] demonstrate small improvement over [24].

Table 6 ZDD node count when representing all Path Delay Faults with two different mappings

circuit	# PDFs	variable per primary line (inputs and branches)				variable per line			
		proposed		reported in [25]		proposed		reported in [25]	
		final	peak	final	peak	final	peak	final	peak
c880	17284	557	559	557	60298	940	941	940	87892
s35932	394282	21310	21312	n/a	n/a	37695	37696	n/a	n/a
s9234	489708	3884	3886	3884	435372	9481	9482	9484	11907784
usb_funct	634744	22844	22846	n/a	n/a	42183	42184	n/a	n/a
c2670	1359768	1558	1560	1710	248346	2751	2752	2979	334194
c7552	1452986	4247	4249	4247	751170	7759	7760	7759	1150772
c1908	1458114	1061	1063	1061	270830	1941	1942	1941	595826
s38584	2161442	20639	20641	20643	1580012	40044	40045	40048	3828412
c5315	2682610	3186	3188	3186	295358	5493	5494	5493	516110
s13207	2690638	5828	5830	5928	630574	13807	13808	14186	1591254
s38417	2782878	17544	17546	17824	3018988	39801	39802	40339	6036954
mem_ctr	3392214	20067	20069	n/a	n/a	37193	37194	n/a	n/a
c1355	8346432	850	852	850	293314	1396	1397	1396	554946
c3540	57353342	1921	1923	1921	778764	3590	3591	3590	1305094
b14	186784978	12131	12133	n/a	n/a	21953	21954	n/a	n/a
b21	298764622	17777	17779	n/a	n/a	31679	31680	n/a	n/a
s15850	329476070	6664	6666	6686	1188586	16439	16440	16461	4863698
tv80	415514364	12766	12768	n/a	n/a	24718	24719	n/a	n/a
b20	579584176	24210	24212	n/a	n/a	43897	43898	n/a	n/a
b22	874724656	23205	23207	n/a	n/a	47843	47844	n/a	n/a
systemcaes	945770246	155552	155554	n/a	n/a	30939	30940	n/a	n/a
b15	96511691200	12234	12236	n/a	n/a	20671	20672	n/a	n/a
b17	7.90677E+11	42117	42119	n/a	n/a	72963	72964	n/a	n/a
c6288	1.97887E+20	3904	3906	3904	2951536	6320	6321	6320	8652806

we emulated fault simulation by considering a random number of detected faults (PDFs) at each iteration of the algorithm, which corresponds to the fault simulation of a single test (vector pair). Table 6 lists the ZDD node count for the two different mappings described in Section 2.1. For all circuits the number of PDFs represented is twice the number of structural paths (reported under Column 2). Columns 3-6 consider the more compacted mapping of [25] where a ZDD variable is created only per primary input and per branch (primary lines). Columns 7-10 consider the more generic mapping of [36] where each variable in the ZDD corresponds to a line in the circuit. For each case final and peak node numbers are reported. Final refers to the number of nodes in the final ZDD i.e., the one containing all the PDFs (Z_{det}). Peak refers to the maximum number of nodes that can exist at any time throughout the ZDD construction process. A n/a entry denotes that results for the corresponding circuit are not available. Columns 3 and 4 report the node counts, final and peak, when the proposed ZDD variable ordering is used for the mapping of [25]. Columns 5 and 6 list the same results as reported in [25]. For both cases the final ZDDs (Columns 3 and 5) have as many nodes as the number of branches in the circuit plus two times the number of primary inputs (small differences are attributed to different versions of the circuits). This occurs because the work in [25] uses a variable ordering which follows a topological order of the circuit's lines. Recall that in Section 3 we mention that when using a topological ordering the obtained ZDD has the same final size as that constructed using the reverse topological ordering, although the former increases the construction time and the number of in-

termediate (peak) nodes. This last disadvantage is obvious when comparing the peak node counts (Columns 4 and 6), which are actually those determining the memory footprint of the approach. The proposed ordering bounds the number of intermediate nodes and as a result the number of nodes in the ZDD at any specific time of its construction is bounded to the number of variables plus two. The corresponding result from [25] is by far larger. For completeness, we report the same results for the more generic mapping of [36] (columns 7-8). The results are compared to those in [25] as they outperform those in [36]. Again, the proposed ordering gives significantly better results than those reported in [25] with respect to the number of peak nodes.

6 Conclusions

Representing all the paths in a DAG using a ZDD structure can be much more useful, than using the DAG directly, for a number of path-related problems. In this work we demonstrate, both in theory and in practice, that a DAG can be represented with a ZDD of equal size, when its variables follow an ordering based on the reverse topological order of a DAG's vertices. More importantly, the size of the ZDD throughout its construction is also bounded by the size of the DAG plus one. The impact of the ordering has been evaluated when representing structural paths in digital circuits as well as for the well-known problem of PDF test grading which considers logical paths in circuits. Our findings clearly render ZDD-based path related methodologies with currently questionable scalability applicable

to large industrial designs, among a plethora of other applications.

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